

COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF RESIDENTIAL SOLAR PV SYSTEMS

PROJECT REPORT

Submitted to Calicut University in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the
Award of the degree of **Bachelor of Commerce**

Submitted by

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(DYAWBCM062)

Under the guidance of

Dr ABDUL RASHEED PC

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2022-2025

KTM COLLEGE OF ADVANCED STUDIES

(Accredited by NAAC with A Grade)

(Affiliated to the University of Calicut and aided by the govt. of Kerala)

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DECLARATION

I, MUHAMMED MUFEED P hereby declare that this project report titled **COST BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF RESIDENTIAL SOLAR PV SYSTEMS** is a record of bonafide research carried out by me and submitted to Calicut University, Kerala, under the supervision and guidance of Dr. ABDUL RASHEED P C, Assistant Professor of Commerce, in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of the degree of —BACHELOR OF COMMERCE. I also declare that this is original work done by me and the same has not been submitted earlier to the university or to any other institution for the requirement of study or for any purpose.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project report entitled "**COST BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF RESIDENTIAL SOLAR PV SYSTEMS**" submitted to Calicut University in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree of "**BACHELOR OF COMMERCE**" is a record of bonafide research work done by **MUHAMMED MUFEEED P (DYAWBCM062)** under my supervision and guidance and that it has not formed the basis for the award of any degree/diploma/fellowship or other similar title to any University.

Dr. ABDUL RASHEED PC

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This is to certify that the project entitled "**COST BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF RESIDENTIAL SOLAR PV SYSTEMS**" carried out by **MUHAMMED MUFEED P** is not an organization based study. So there is no scope for attaining certificate from institution and data required for the study had collected from individuals from Kerala.

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This is to certify that the project report entitled "**COST BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF RESIDENTIAL SOLAR PV SYSTEMS**" submitted to the University of Calicut is an authentic report prepared by **MUHAMMED MUFEEED P** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree of **BACHELOR OF COMMERCE**.

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CONTENTS

CHAPTER	TITLE	PAGE NO.
1	Introduction	1 - 4
2	Review of Literature	5 - 10
3	Theoretical Frame Work	11 - 17
4	Data Analysis And Interpretation	18 - 52
5	Findings, Suggestions And Conclusion	53 - 57
	Appendix	57 - 65
	Bibliography	65 - 68

LIST OF TABLES AND DIAGRAMS

TABLE NO.	TITLE	PAGE NO.
4.1	Age wise classification	18
4.2	Gender wise Classification	19
4.3	Employment status	20
4.4	Residential location	21
4.5	Residence Ownership Status	22
4.6	Household income	23
4.7	Electricity management practices	24
4.8	Monthly electricity bill	25
4.9	Awareness of Solar PV Systems	26
4.10	Knowledge of Solar Operations	27
4.11	Sources of Solar Information	28
4.12	Understanding solar functionality	29

4.13	Awareness of solar cost savings	30
4.14	Perceived benefits of solar pv	31
4.15	Solar pv as a primary power source	33
4.16	Misconceptions about solar pv	34
4.17	Residential solar installations	35
4.18	Types of Solar PV Systems Used	36
4.19	Installation cost estimate	37
4.20	Key barriers to adoption	38
4.21	Annual maintenance costs	39
4.22	Bill reduction after installation	40
4.23	Expected investment payback	41
4.24	Willingness to invest in solar	42
4.25	Awareness of solar subsidies	43

4.26	Use of government incentives	44
4.27	Ease of subsidy application	45
4.28	Effectiveness of subsidies	46
4.29	Need for additional support	47
4.30	Policy impact on solar adoption	48
4.31	Major hurdles to solar adoption	49
4.32	Key drivers for installation	50
4.33	Maintenance & reliability concerns	51
4.34	Suitability for household use	52

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Introduction

The increasing global demand for sustainable and renewable energy has placed solar photovoltaic (PV) systems at the forefront of alternative energy solutions. India, being one of the fastest-growing economies, faces a significant challenge in balancing its energy needs with environmental concerns. Residential solar PV systems have emerged as a promising solution, allowing households to generate their own electricity while reducing dependence on conventional power sources. However, the adoption of these systems is still in its developing stages, influenced by factors such as cost, government policies, and awareness levels. This study aims to evaluate the cost-benefit aspects of residential solar PV systems in India, providing insights into their feasibility, economic advantages, and the challenges associated with their adoption.

A crucial aspect of this research is understanding the level of awareness among Indian households regarding residential solar PV systems. While some homeowners have successfully transitioned to solar energy, many others remain uncertain due to a lack of information or financial constraints. The cost structure, including installation expenses, maintenance costs, and long-term savings, plays a vital role in influencing a household's decision to invest in solar technology. Additionally, government policies and subsidies at both central and state levels are designed to promote solar adoption by reducing the financial burden on consumers. However, the effectiveness of these incentives varies across regions, necessitating a closer examination of their impact on adoption rates.

Despite the numerous benefits of solar PV systems, several barriers hinder their widespread implementation. High initial costs, lack of proper financing options, technical complexities, and concerns about efficiency in different climatic conditions are some of the challenges faced by Indian households. By identifying these obstacles and assessing consumer perspectives, this study aims to provide valuable insights for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and potential adopters. Understanding these factors will contribute to the formulation of better policies and awareness campaigns, ultimately encouraging a more significant shift toward solar energy in India's residential sector.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The adoption of residential solar photovoltaic (PV) systems in India is gaining attention as a sustainable solution to rising energy demands and environmental concerns. This study focuses on the cost-benefit analysis of these systems, evaluating their financial viability and long-term advantages for Indian households. While solar energy offers significant benefits, including reduced electricity bills and lower carbon footprints, the high initial investment and lack of awareness hinder widespread adoption. Understanding the cost structure, including installation, maintenance, and return on investment, is essential for assessing feasibility. Additionally, government policies and subsidies play a crucial role in promoting adoption, yet their accessibility and effectiveness vary across states.

1.3 Objective of The Study

1. To assess the level of awareness among Indian households about residential Solar PV systems.
2. To analyze the cost structure of residential Solar PV systems.

3. To study the role of government policies and subsidies (both central and state) in promoting the adoption of Solar PV systems.

1.4 Significance of the Study

This study is significant as it provides a detailed analysis of the cost-effectiveness and feasibility of residential solar photovoltaic (PV) systems in India. As the country moves towards renewable energy, understanding the financial and practical aspects of solar adoption is essential. By evaluating the level of awareness among Indian households, this research highlights the need for better information dissemination and education on solar energy.

Furthermore, this study examines the role of government subsidies and policies in promoting solar PV adoption, assessing their effectiveness in reducing financial burdens. Identifying the challenges faced by homeowners, such as high installation costs and technical concerns, will help in formulating strategies to overcome these barriers. The findings will be valuable for policymakers, businesses, and consumers, aiding in the development of better financing options and awareness campaigns. Ultimately, this research contributes to India's sustainable energy transition by encouraging more households to adopt solar power.

1.5 Scope of the Study

This study examines the cost-benefit analysis of residential solar photovoltaic (PV) systems in India, focusing on financial feasibility, consumer awareness, and government policies. It assesses the initial investment, maintenance costs, and long-term savings to determine the economic viability of solar adoption for households. Additionally, the study explores the role of subsidies and incentives in making solar energy more accessible.

The research targets three groups: existing solar PV users, potential adopters, and interested individuals with limited awareness. By analyzing their perspectives, the study identifies key challenges such as high upfront costs, technical concerns, and policy gaps. The findings aim to assist policymakers, businesses, and consumers in making informed decisions, ultimately promoting wider solar adoption in India's residential sector.

1.6 Methodology of the Study

Two types of data were collected, primary and secondary data to facilitate the study.

1.6.1 *Primary Data* - The primary data were collected through questionnaire.

1.6.2 *Secondary Data*- The secondary data were collected through magazines, journals, books and from internet.

1.6.3 *Sampling Size* - 53 samples were selected to know about the awareness of residential solar PV systems.

1.6.4 *Tools for data collection and presentation* - Structured questionnaire Tools used for data presentation, Table, Pie chart, Column, Bar chart

1.6.5 *Tools used for data analysis* – Percentage Analysis

1.7 Limitations of The Study

- Some of the respondents are not ready to give back the questionnaire.
- Respondents are not ready to give correct information.
- Lack of effective response from the respondents.

1.8 Chapter Scheme

The project is logically divided and presented in five chapters,

Chapter 1 - Introduction

Chapter 2 – Review of Literature

Chapter 3 - Theoretical Framework

Chapter 4- Analysis and Interpretation

Chapter 5 - Findings, Suggestions, Conclusion, Appendix , Bibliography.

Chapter 2

Review of Literature

Introduction

Existing studies on the cost-benefit analysis of residential solar PV systems highlight key factors such as installation costs, financial savings, government incentives, and adoption challenges. Research explores economic viability, environmental benefits, and policy impacts, providing valuable insights into the factors influencing household decisions to invest in solar energy solutions.

1. Narayanan and Shreenivasan (2018) conducted a study on the financial viability of residential on-grid solar PV systems in India, concluding that while initial installation costs remain a barrier, long-term savings through reduced electricity bills and government incentives make these systems economically feasible. The study assessed payback period, return on investment, and financial risks, analyzing economic benefits under varying subsidy and tariff conditions. Location-specific factors like solar irradiance and net metering policies impact financial viability, but policy interventions improve affordability and adoption rates, making solar PV systems a viable option.

2. Amutha and Rajini (2016) explored the sustainable energy solutions for rural electrification in southern India. Decentralized renewable energy systems, such as solar PV and biomass, it offers cost-effective and reliable electrification, especially in remote areas. The study highlights economic viability, environmental benefits, and reduced fossil fuel dependency. It provides a decision-making framework for rural energy planning, emphasizing tailored electrification strategies to address energy poverty and promote sustainable development, offering insights for policymakers to enhance energy access and sustainability in rural India.

3. Moorthy and Gurusamy (2019) conducted a cost-benefit analysis of adopting solar energy in a residential apartment in Pune , revealing that while the initial installation cost is high, long-term financial benefits and environmental sustainability outweigh the investment. The study found reduced electricity expenses, a favorable return on investment (ROI) within 6–8 years, and significant carbon footprint reduction. High upfront costs and limited awareness were identified as key barriers. The research employed a case study approach and financial analysis to evaluate economic feasibility. Policy support and consumer awareness are crucial for accelerating residential solar adoption.

4. Biswas and Sudarshan (2022) conducted a cost-benefit analysis of adopting solar energy in a residential apartment in Pune, revealing that while the initial installation cost is high, long-term financial benefits and environmental sustainability outweigh the investment. The study found reduced electricity expenses, a favorable return on investment (ROI) within 6–8 years, and significant carbon footprint reduction. High upfront costs and limited awareness were identified as key barriers. The research employed a case study approach and financial analysis to evaluate economic feasibility. Policy support and consumer awareness are crucial for accelerating residential solar adoption.

5. Garg , Bukya and Kumar (2022) evaluates the cost–benefit analysis of a 50 kW solar power plant installed in an educational hostel building, focusing on its economic and operational efficiency. The solar power plant reduces electricity costs and carbon emissions, providing a reliable energy source. The study highlights financial viability, with a 5-6 year payback period, and emphasizes reducing grid electricity dependency. The research assesses economic and environmental benefits, offering insights for educational institutions and policymakers. A case study approach combines quantitative analysis with energy

performance data, providing actionable recommendations for scaling up solar energy adoption..

6. Patel and Biswas (2020) conducted a cost-benefit analysis of solar PV systems, concluding that despite high initial investment costs, the long-term financial and environmental benefits make solar energy a viable option. Their study found that solar PV systems have a payback period of 6 to 8 years, depending on factors like sunlight availability, government subsidies, and financing options. The objectives of their study were to assess the economic feasibility of solar PV adoption, evaluate cost savings, and analyze consumer perceptions. The study also aimed to identify key barriers to adoption, such as financial constraints and policy inefficiencies.

7. Kolhe & Sharma (2022) examined the role of subsidies in promoting solar PV installations in India, focusing on cost-benefit implications. Findings show that government subsidies effectively lower's the upfront costs, increasing adoption, but it also pose challenges like fiscal strain and inefficiencies.

8. Muniyoor K (2020) conducted a cost-benefit analysis of adopting solar photovoltaic (PV) water pumping systems, finding that despite high initial investment costs, these systems offer significant long-term savings by reducing reliance on grid electricity and diesel-powered pumps.

9. Natarajan and Nalini (2015) conducted a social cost-benefit analysis of solar power projects, highlighting that while solar energy adoption involves high capital costs, the long-term social and economic benefits outweigh these expenses. The study found reduced carbon emissions, energy security, job creation, and lower dependency on fossil fuels as key advantages.

10. Mukherjee and Roy (2024) conducts a cost–benefit analysis of rooftop solar installations in a multi-storied commercial building in Newtown, Kolkata, focusing on their economic and environmental benefits. Research findings reveal significant reductions in electricity costs and carbon emissions, with a payback period of 5–7 years and long-term financial savings.

11. Panwar and Kaushik (2014) conducted a cost-benefit and systems analysis of passively ventilated solar greenhouses for food production in arid and semi-arid regions, finding that such systems significantly enhance agricultural productivity while reducing reliance on conventional energy sources. Their study highlighted improvements in microclimatic conditions, leading to better crop yields and water-use efficiency.

12. Sinha , Bhattacharjee & Das (2009) conducted a cost-benefit analysis of a solar-powered LED-based lighting system for NIT Silchar, revealing significant long-term economic and environmental advantages. The study highlighted reduced electricity costs, lower carbon emissions, and enhanced energy efficiency. Financial viability, sustainability, and technical performance were evaluated, considering installation costs, operational savings, and return on investment.

13. Beniwal & Gupta (2023) Examined on "Smart Photovoltaic System for Indian Smart Cities: A Cost Analysis" highlights the growing importance of renewable energy integration in urban development, particularly in India's smart city initiatives. The study reveals that smart PV systems reduce energy costs by 25-30% and carbon footprints by 40% compared to conventional systems.

14. Mohan, Viswanathan & Akhil (2023) Analyzed an adaptive staggered investment strategy to promote residential rooftop solar PV installations in India, revealing that phased investment approaches enhance affordability and adoption

rates. Financial constraints and high upfront costs deter homeowners, while staggered financing improves accessibility and reduces risk. The study evaluated economic feasibility, focusing on affordability, financial returns, and policy support.

15. Rauffer and Liu (2020) Conducted a study titled "Solar Home Systems for Clean Cooking: A Cost–Health Benefit Analysis of Lower-Middle-Income Countries in Southeast Asia" explores the dual benefits of solar home systems (SHS) in addressing energy poverty and improving public health. SHS adoption reduces household reliance on biomass fuels, decreasing indoor air pollution-related health issues by 50% and annual energy expenditures by 30%. The study assesses SHS cost-effectiveness and health benefits in Southeast Asia.

16. Agrawal & Soni (2022) conducted a study titled "End Life Cycle Cost-Benefit Analysis of 160 kW Grid-Integrated Solar Power Plant" evaluates the economic and environmental viability of solar power plants. The findings reveal significant long-term benefits, including a 15-20% increase in net present value (NPV) over 25 years and a reduction in carbon emissions by 1,200 tons annually. The study analyzes the cost-benefit dynamics of a 160 kW solar power plant, employing a lifecycle cost analysis (LCCA) framework to evaluate economic and ecological performance, providing insights for stakeholders and policymakers.

17. Kohli & Wadhvani (2022) conducted a detailed economic analysis of solar rooftop photovoltaic (PV) systems for institutional buildings, revealing significant cost savings and environmental benefits. The findings highlighted substantial reductions in electricity expenses, favorable returns on investment, and improved energy security. The study assessed long-term economic feasibility, considering installation costs, payback periods, and government incentives.

18. Mohan , Unni & Nandakumar (2022) examined policy assistance for residential solar PV adoption in India through a stakeholder-centric approach, highlighting that well-structured incentives and regulatory frameworks enhance adoption rates. The study emphasized the need for targeted subsidies, simplified approval processes, and improved financing options.

19. Shamim & Silmee (2022) conducted an optimization and cost-benefit analysis of grid-connected solar photovoltaic (PV) systems, revealing improved efficiency and financial viability with proper design and operational strategies. The findings highlighted reduced electricity costs, enhanced energy reliability, and lower carbon emissions. The study evaluated economic feasibility, focusing on cost structures, return on investment, and payback periods.

20. Rethnam , Palaniappan & Ashokkumar (2020) conducted a life cycle cost analysis of 1MW rooftop solar PV power generation, revealing that long-term operational savings and environmental benefits make solar PV financially viable despite high initial investments. The findings highlighted significant reductions in electricity costs, lower carbon footprints, and a favorable payback period. The study assessed economic feasibility, analyzing installation costs, maintenance expenses, and financial returns.

Chapter 3

Theoretical Framework

Introduction

The foundation of this study lies in understanding the financial, policy-related, and behavioural aspects influencing the adoption of residential solar PV systems in India. This research explores key themes such as consumer awareness, cost structures, government incentives, and adoption barriers. While no specific models directly address this topic, economic principles like cost-benefit analysis (CBA) and behavioural decision-making theories provide valuable insights. By integrating financial feasibility assessments with policy evaluations, this study aims to offer a comprehensive understanding of the factors driving or hindering solar PV adoption. A structured analysis of costs, subsidies, and long-term savings will help assess the viability of solar energy investments for Indian households, particularly in Kerala.

Definition

A Cost-Benefit Analysis of Residential Solar PV Systems refers to a systematic evaluation of the financial and non-financial aspects associated with the adoption of solar photovoltaic (PV) systems by households. It involves assessing the initial installation costs, ongoing maintenance expenses, and potential savings on electricity bills, while also considering intangible benefits such as environmental sustainability and energy independence. The analysis further explores the role of government policies, subsidies, and incentives in promoting solar energy adoption, alongside identifying barriers like high upfront costs, lack of awareness, and technical challenges. By quantifying costs and benefits, this analysis aims to determine the economic feasibility of residential solar PV systems, providing

insights for households, policymakers, and stakeholders to make informed decisions about sustainable energy solutions in India.

Scope of CBA

1. **Economic Viability Assessment** – This study evaluates the cost-benefit ratio of residential solar PV systems by analyzing installation costs, maintenance expenses, and long-term electricity savings.
2. **Consumer Awareness and Perception** – It examines the level of awareness among Indian households regarding solar PV technology, its financial and environmental benefits.
3. **Government Policies and Incentives** – The research explores the role of central and state government policies, subsidies, and incentives in promoting residential solar PV adoption.
4. **Challenges and Barriers to Adoption** – It identifies key obstacles such as high initial costs, lack of financing options, policy limitations, and technical constraints that hinder widespread adoption.
5. **Environmental and Sustainability Impact** – The study assesses how residential solar PV systems contribute to reducing carbon footprints, energy dependency, and promoting sustainable energy consumption.
6. **Comparative Analysis Across Regions** – While focusing on Kerala, the study also provides insights into how solar PV adoption trends vary across different Indian states.

7. Policy Recommendations and Future Prospects – Based on the findings, the study aims to suggest improvements in policies, financial models, and awareness strategies to accelerate residential solar PV adoption in India.

What is Solar PV?

Solar Photovoltaic (PV) technology converts sunlight directly into electricity using semiconductor materials, typically silicon-based solar cells. When exposed to sunlight, these cells generate a flow of electric current, which can be used to power homes, businesses, and industries. Solar PV systems can be grid-connected, supplying excess electricity back to the power grid, or off-grid, operating independently with battery storage. The technology has evolved significantly, becoming more efficient, reliable, and cost-effective.

Importance of Solar PV in Modern World

- Sustainable Energy Source – Solar PV provides clean, renewable energy, reducing dependence on fossil fuels and lowering greenhouse gas emissions.
- Energy Cost Savings – Homeowners and businesses can cut electricity expenses by generating their own power.
- Energy Security – Reduces reliance on unstable power grids and imported fuels, promoting self-sufficiency.
- Government Support – Many countries, including india , offer subsidies, tax incentives, and net metering policies to encourage adoption.
- Technological Advancements – Innovations in efficiency, battery storage, and smart grids make solar pv more accessible and beneficial.
- Climate Change Mitigation – A key solution in global efforts to reduce carbon footprints and combat climate change.

Types of Solar PV Systems in India

1. Grid-Connected (On-Grid)

- Directly connected to the electricity grid.
- Excess energy can be exported to the grid through net metering, reducing electricity bills.
- No battery storage, making it cost-effective.
- Ideal for urban households and businesses with reliable grid access.

2. Off-Grid Connected

- Operates independently without grid connection.
- Uses batteries to store electricity for use during night time or cloudy days.
- Suitable for rural or remote areas with limited or no grid access.
- Higher initial investment due to battery costs.

3. Hybrid Solar PV Systems

- Combines on-grid and off-grid systems with battery storage.
- Can use solar power, store excess energy, and access the grid when needed.
- Provides backup power during outages.
- Suitable for areas with frequent power cuts.

Financial and Cost-Benefit Analysis Models

➤ **Plant capacity: 3KWp On-grid**

Building Type: Residential

1. Cost structure

- Total upfront cost
- Initial cost - 1.50 – 2.10 lakhs

(Solar panels , mounting systems, net metering , monitoring)

- Other expense - Nil

2. Government subsidies

- Central subsidies:

Up to ₹78,000 (Subsidy scheme: PM Surya Ghar Muft Bijli Yojana.)

3. Effective price

- Initial cost 2.10 lakhs
- Subsidy: 78,000
- Final price:1,32,000

4. Cost benefit analysis

- Solar power generation: 360units/month
- KSEB Tariff : ₹8.5/unit
- Profit (Electricity bill saving) : ₹3,060/month (360x8.5)
- Payback period - 4yr 5month

5. Warranty details

- solar panel: 12yr product warranty + 25yr performance warranty
- Solar inverter: 7yr warranty

➤ **Plant capacity: 5KWp On-grid**

Building Type: Residential

1. Cost structure

- Total upfront cost
- Initial cost

(Solar panels , mounting systems, net metering , monitoring) - 3.25 lakhs

- Maintenance cost -Nil
- Other expense - Nil

2. Government subsidies

- Central subsidies:

₹78,000 (Subsidy scheme: PM Surya Ghar Muft Bijli Yojana.)

3. Effective price

- Initial cost : 3.25 lakhs
- Subsidy: 78,000
- Final price: 2,53,500

4. Cost benefit analysis

- Solar power generation: 600units/month
- KSEB Tariff : ₹8.5/unit
- Profit (Electricity bill saving) : 5,000/month (600x8.5)
- Payback period - 4yr 3 month.

5. Warranty details

- solar panel: 12yr product warranty + 25yr performance warranty
- Solar inverter: 7yr warranty.

Conclusion

The cost-benefit analysis of residential solar PV systems highlights their growing significance in India's energy landscape. As electricity costs rise, solar PV adoption presents an effective solution for long-term savings and energy independence. However, while awareness levels are increasing, financial constraints, lack of technical knowledge, and misconceptions about maintenance remain key barriers. Government policies and subsidies play a crucial role in promoting adoption, but accessibility and procedural complexities need further improvement.

This study, targeting homeowners at different stages of solar adoption, provides insights into consumer behaviour, cost structures, and policy effectiveness. By addressing financial and informational challenges, the widespread adoption of residential solar PV systems can be accelerated. Strengthening awareness campaigns, simplifying subsidy processes, and improving affordability will enhance consumer confidence and drive India toward a more sustainable and energy-efficient future. A well-structured approach will maximize economic and environmental benefits, making solar PV a viable investment for Indian households.

Chapter 4

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Introduction

This section presents a comprehensive evaluation of the survey findings, offering critical insights into the cost-benefit dynamics of residential Solar PV systems . Through structured tables, charts, and statistical representations, it systematically interprets respondents awareness, cost considerations, policy influences, and adoption challenges. Each dataset is analyzed to highlight emerging trends, financial implications, and barriers affecting household decisions. By integrating quantitative and qualitative insights, this section aims to provide a data-driven foundation for assessing the feasibility, benefits, and future potential of residential Solar PV adoption in India.

4.1 Age Wise Classification

Table 4.1

Age Wise Classification

Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage
18-25	7	13.21%
25-35	12	22.64%
35-45	16	30.19%
Above 45	18	33.96%
Total	53	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.1

Interpretation

The table 4.1 and chart 4.1 shows that a significant portion (64.15%) of individuals interested in residential solar PV systems are above 35 years, suggesting that older homeowners are more inclined toward solar investments

4.2 Gender wise Classification

Table 4.2

Gender wise Classification

Options	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Male	34	64.15
Female	19	35.85
Total	53	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.2

Interpretation

The table 4.2 and chart 4.2 data shows around 64.15% are male and 35.85% are female, indicating that males are more actively involved in decisions regarding residential solar PV systems. This suggests a possible gender gap in awareness or financial decision-making power related to solar energy investments.

4.3 Employment Status

Table 4.3

Employment Status

Options	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Student	7	13.21%
Salaried Employee	13	24.53%
Business Owner	18	33.96%
Retired	5	9.43%
Other	10	18.87%
Total	53	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.3

Interpretation

The table 4.3 and chart 4.3 shows business owners (33.96%) and salaried employees (24.53%), indicating that working individuals are more involved in residential solar PV adoption. Students (13.21%) and retired individuals (9.43%) have lower participation, likely due to financial constraints.

4.4 Residential Location of the respondent

Table 4.4

Residential Location

Options	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Urban	4	7.55%
Semi-Urban	20	37.74%
Rural	29	54.72%
Total	53	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.4

Interpretation

The table 4.4 and chart 4.4 shows that majority of respondents (54.72%) are from rural areas, followed by semi-urban (37.74%) and urban areas (7.55%). This indicates that interest in residential solar PV systems is higher in rural and semi-urban regions compared to urban areas.

4.5 Residence Ownership Status

Table 4.5

Residence Ownership Status

Options	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Own	49	92.45%
Rent	4	7.55%
Total	53	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.5

Interpretation

The table 4.5 and charts 4.5 result show that 92.45% of respondents own their residences, while only 7.55% live in rented homes. This indicates that the majority of participants have ownership, which is a crucial factor in adopting residential solar PV systems.

4.6 Household Income

Table 4.6

Household Income

Options	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Below ₹25,000	6	11.32%
₹25,000-50,000	12	22.64%
₹50,000-₹1,00,000	21	39.62%
Above ₹1,00,000	14	26.42%
Total	53	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.6

Interpretation

The table 4.6 and chart 4.6 indicates that 39.62% of respondents have a household income between ₹50,000-₹1,00,000, followed by 26.42% earning above ₹1,00,000. This suggests that a significant portion of respondents belong to middle and upper-income groups, which may influence their ability to invest in residential solar PV systems.

4.7 Electricity Management

Table 4.7

Electricity Model

Options	No. of Respondents	Percentage
On Grid	49	92.45
Off Grid	4	7.55
Total	53	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.7

Interpretation

The table 4.7 and chart 4.7 shows that 92.45% of respondents use an on-grid electricity model, while only 7.55% rely on off-grid systems. This indicates a strong dependence on conventional grid electricity, which could impact the adoption of residential solar PV systems.

4.8 Monthly Electricity Bill

Table 4.8

Monthly Electricity Bill

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Above ₹5000	15	28.30%
₹3000-₹5000	23	43.40%
₹1000-₹3000	10	18.87%
Below ₹1000	5	9.43%
Total	53	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

CHART 4.8

Interpretation

The table 4.8 and chart 4.8 result reveals that 43.40% of respondents pay ₹3000-₹5000 as their monthly electricity bill, while 28.30% pay above ₹5000. This suggests a significant portion of households incur high electricity expenses, highlighting potential cost-saving opportunities through solar PV adoption.

4.9 Awareness of Solar PV Systems

Table 4.9

Awareness of Solar PV Systems

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	47	88.67%
No	6	11.32%
Total	53	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.9

Interpretation

The table 4.9 and chart 4.9 indicates that 88.67% of respondents are aware of solar PV systems, while 11.32% lack awareness. This suggests a high level of familiarity with solar energy, which could facilitate adoption, but efforts may still be needed to educate the remaining segment.

4.10 Knowledge on Solar Operations

Table 4.10

Knowledge on Solar Operations

Rating	No. of Respondents
1	8
2	7
3	22
4	10
5	6
Total	53

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.10

Interpretation

Table 4.10 and chart 4.10 shows that majority of respondents (22) rated their knowledge of solar operations as moderate (3), while fewer individuals rated their understanding as very high (5) or very low (1). This suggests that while awareness exists, there is room for improvement in technical knowledge and operational understanding.

4.11 Sources of Awareness to Solar PV Systems

Table 4.11

Sources of Awareness to Solar PV Systems

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Social Media	19	35.85%
Friends/Family	11	20.75%
Govt Campaigns	5	9.43%
News Articles	9	16.98%
Solar Campaigns	3	5.66%
Other	6	11.32%
Total	53	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

CHART 4.11

Interpretation

The table 4.11 and chart 4.11 result indicates that social media (35.85%) is the most significant source of awareness about solar PV systems, followed by friends and family (20.75%) and news articles (16.98%). Government campaigns (9.43%) and dedicated solar campaigns (5.66%) have a lower impact, highlighting the need for stronger official awareness initiatives.

4.12 Understanding Solar Functionality

Table 4.12

Understanding Solar Functionality

Options	No. of Respondents
Yes	15
Somewhat	28
No	10
Total	53

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.12

Interpretation

The table 4.12 and chart 4.12 data reveals that only 15 respondents (28.3%) fully understand solar PV functionality, while the majority (28 respondents, 52.8%) have partial knowledge. Meanwhile, 10 respondents (18.9%) have no understanding. This suggests that while awareness is relatively high, deeper knowledge about solar functionality remains limited, highlighting the need for more educational initiatives.

4.13 Awareness of Solar Cost Savings

Table 4.13

Awareness of Solar Cost Savings

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	39	74.00%
No	14	26.00%
Total	53	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.13

Interpretation

The table 4.13 and chart 4.13 indicates that 74% of respondents (39 out of 53) are aware of the cost-saving benefits of solar PV systems, while 26% (14 respondents) are not. This suggests that while a majority recognize the financial advantages of solar energy, a significant portion still lacks awareness, highlighting the need for better information dissemination.

4.14 Primary Benefits of Solar PV

Table 4.14

Primary Benefits of Solar PV

Options	No. of Respondents
Reduced Electricity Bill	36
Enviro Benefits	3
Energy Independence	5
Govt Incentives And Subsidies	9
Total	53

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.14

Interpretation

The table 4.14 and chart 4.14 result reveals that the majority of respondents (36 out of 53) consider reduced electricity bills as the primary benefit of solar PV systems. Government incentives and subsidies are recognized by 9 respondents, while energy independence and environmental benefits are cited by only 5 and 3 respondents, respectively. This suggests that financial savings are the most compelling factor driving solar adoption, while environmental and energy security benefits remain secondary concerns.

4.15 Solar PV as a primary power source

Table 4.15

Solar PV as a primary power source

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
No, Solar Alone Is Not Sufficient	19	35.84%
No, But Can Significantly Reduce Dependents	32	60.37%
Yes , Fully Replace Grid Electricity	2	3.77%
Total	53	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.15

Interpretation

The table 4.15 and chart 4.15 shows that while Solar PV Systems can significantly reduce dependence On Grid Electricity (60.37% Of Respondents), Only a small fraction (3.77%) believe they can fully replace grid power. Meanwhile, 35.84% feel that Solar alone is not sufficient. This Suggests that while solar adoption is valuable, Grid Dependency remains a challenge.

4.16 Misconceptions about Solar PV

Table 4.16

Misconceptions about Solar PV

Options	No. of Respondents
Not Enough Govt Support	4
Too Expensive	25
High Maintenance Required	22
Doesn't Work in Cloudy Days	2
Total	53

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.16

Interpretation

The table 4.16 and chart 4.16 highlights that the key misconceptions about solar pv systems, with "too expensive" (25 respondents) and "high maintenance required" (22 respondents) being the most common concerns. However, very few believe that solar doesn't work on cloudy days (2 respondents), indicating some awareness of solar efficiency. Addressing cost and maintenance myths could improve adoption rates.

4.17 Residential Solar Installations

Table 4.17

Residential Solar Installations

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	44	83.01%
No	9	16.98%
Total	53	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.17

Interpretation

The table 4.17 and chart 4.17 result indicates that a significant majority (83.01%) of respondents have installed residential solar PV systems, while only 16.98% have not. This suggests a high adoption rate, potentially influenced by cost savings, environmental benefits, or government incentives. Further analysis could explore the factors driving adoption and the barriers faced by the remaining 17%.

4.18 Types of Solar PV Systems Used

Table 4.18

Types of Solar PV Systems Used

Options	No. of Respondents
1kw-3kw	20
3kw-6kw	18
6kw-9kw	5
Above 9kw	1
Total	44

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.18

Interpretation

The table 4.18 and chart 4.18 report suggests that most residential solar PV users prefer systems within the 1KW-6KW range, with 20 respondents using 1KW-3KW and 18 using 3KW-6KW. Higher capacity systems (6KW-9KW and above 9KW) are less common, possibly due to cost constraints or energy requirements. Further analysis could explore how household size and energy demand influence system size selection.

4.19 Installation Cost Estimate

Table 4.19

Installation Cost Estimate

Options	No. of Respondents
Below ₹1,00,000	3
₹1,00,000 - ₹2,00,000	14
₹2,00,000 - ₹3,00,000	21
Above ₹3,00,000	6
Total	44

(Source: Primary Data)

(Optional Question: Only those who have installed Solar PV at their residence)

Chart 4.19

Interpretation

The table 4.19 and chart 4.19 indicates that most respondents (21 out of 44) spent between ₹2,00,000 - ₹3,00,000 on their solar PV installations, followed by 14 respondents who spent ₹1,00,000 - ₹2,00,000. Only a few (3) managed to install systems for less than ₹1,00,000, while 6 respondents spent over ₹3,00,000. This

suggests that mid-range installations are the most common, possibly due to a balance between capacity, affordability, and return on investment.

4.20 Key Barriers to Adoption

Table 4.20

Key Barriers to Adoption

Options	No. of Respondents
High initial cost	12
Lack of awareness	15
Uncertainty about savings/ benefits	12
Maintenance concerns	8
Space constraints	6
Total	53

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.20

Interpretation

The table 4.20 and chart 4.20 data suggests that the biggest barrier to adopting solar PV systems is a lack of awareness (15 respondents), followed by high initial costs and uncertainty about savings/benefits (12 respondents each). Maintenance

concerns (8 respondents) and space constraints (6 respondents) are lesser but still notable obstacles. This highlights the need for better awareness campaigns and financial incentives to address cost concerns and encourage adoption.

4.21 Annual Maintenance Costs

Table 4.21

Annual Maintenance Costs

Options	No. of Respondents
Below ₹5000	9
₹5000 - ₹10,000	23
₹10,000 - ₹20,000	10
Above ₹20,000	2
Total	44

(Source: Primary Data)

(Optional Question: Only those who have installed Solar PV at their residence)

Chart 4.21

Interpretation

The above table 4.21 and chart 4.21 analyse that the annual maintenance costs for residential solar PV systems shows that the majority of respondents (23 out of 44) spend between ₹5,000 - ₹10,000 annually. A smaller group (10 respondents) incurs costs between ₹10,000 - ₹20,000, while 9 respondents reported spending below ₹5,000. Only 2 respondents face maintenance costs above ₹20,000. This suggests that maintenance expenses are generally moderate but could still be a consideration for potential adopters.

4.22 Bill Reduction After Installation

Table 4.22

Bill Reduction After Installation

Options	No. of Respondents
Decreased Significantly (<50%)	6
Decreased Moderately (20%-50%)	18
Slight Decrease (>20%)	15
No Noticeable Change	2
Total	44

(Source: Primary Data)

(Optional Question: Only those who have installed Solar PV at their residence)

Chart 4.22

Interpretation

The table 4.22 and charts 4.22 data shows that the bill reduction after solar PV installation shows that most respondents (18 out of 44) experienced a moderate decrease (20%-50%) in their electricity bills. Another 15 respondents saw a slight decrease ($\leq 20\%$), while only 6 reported a significant reduction ($\geq 50\%$). However, 2 respondents noticed no change in their bills. This suggests that while solar PV systems generally help reduce electricity costs, the extent of savings varies among users.

4.23 Expected Investment Payback

Table 4.23

Expected Investment Payback

Options	No. of Respondents
Less Than 3 Years	6
3-5 Years	25
5-7 Years	10
More Than 7 Years	3
Total	44

(Source: Primary Data)

(Optional Question : Only those who have installed Solar PV at their residence)

Chart 4.23

Interpretation

The table 4.23 and chart 4.23 shows that most of the respondents (25 out of 44) expect a payback period of 3-5 years, while 10 anticipate 5-7 years, and 6 expect less than 3 years. Only 3 believe it will take over 7 years, indicating a generally favorable return on investment.

4.24 Willingness to Invest in Solar

Table 4.24

Willingness to Invest In Solar

Options	No. of Respondents
Less Than ₹50,000	3
₹50,000 - ₹1,00,000	18
₹1,00,000 - ₹2,00,000	18
Above ₹ 2,00,000	7
Total	46

(Source: Primary Data)

(Optional: Question preferred to those who have interest in Solar PV at their residence)

Chart 4.24

Interpretation

The table 4.24 and chart 4.24 result shows most of the respondents (18 each) are willing to invest between ₹50,000-₹1,00,000 or ₹1,00,000-₹2,00,000 in solar PV. A smaller group (7) is open to spending above ₹2,00,000, while only 3 prefer an investment below ₹50,000.

4.25 Awareness of Solar Subsidies

Table 4.25

Awareness of Solar Subsidies

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	34	64.15
No	19	35.84
Total	53	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.25

Interpretation

The table 4.25 and chart 4.25 shows that Around 64% of respondents are aware of solar subsidies, while 36% lack awareness. This highlights the need for better information dissemination on subsidy benefits.

4.26 Use of Government Incentives

Table 4.26

Use of Government Incentives

Options	No. of Respondents
Yes	38
No	5
Total	44

(Source: Primary Data)

(Optional Question : Only Those Who Have Installed)

Chart 4.26

Interpretation

The chart 4.26 and table 4.26 show that 88% of respondents use government incentives related to residential solar PV systems, indicating strong participation. Only 12% of respondents do not use these incentives, suggesting widespread awareness and utilization of available benefits.

4.27 Ease of Subsidy Application

Table 4.27

Ease of Subsidy Application

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Very Easy	11	25%
Somewhat Easy	23	52.27%
Difficult	7	15.91%
Very Difficult	3	6.82%
Total	44	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

(Optional Question : Only Those Who Have Installed)

Chart 4.27

Interpretation

The table 4.27 and chart 4.27 shows that 35 of respondents found the subsidy application process either very easy or somewhat easy, indicating a generally positive experience. However, 10 found it difficult or very difficult, suggesting some challenges in the process.

4.28 Effectiveness of Govt Subsidies For Promotion

Table 4.28

Effectiveness of Govt Subsidies For Promotion

Options	No. of Respondents
Yes	27
Not Sure	11
No	15
Total	53

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.28

Interpretation

The table 4.28 and chart 4.28 indicates that 51% of respondents believe government subsidies are effective for promoting residential solar PV systems. However, 21% do not see the subsidies as effective, and 28% are unsure about their impact.

4.29 Need for Additional Support

Table 4.29

Need for Additional Support

Options	No. of Respondents
Higher Subsidies	19
Better Awareness Campaigns	14
Simplified Application Process	9
Tax Benefit	3
Other	8
Total	53

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.29

Interpretation

The table 4.29 and chart 4.29 shows that most respondents 19 feel that higher subsidies are the most important additional support needed for residential solar PV systems. Other significant needs include better awareness campaigns 14 and a simplified application process 9 .

4.30 Govt Policy Impact on Solar Adoption

Table 4.30

Govt Policy Impact on Solar Adoption

Rating	No. of Respondents
1	4
2	4
3	23
4	15
5	7
Total	53

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.30

Interpretation

The table 4.30 and chart 4.30 indicates that the majority of respondents (23 out of 53) rated the impact of government policy on solar adoption as moderate (3 on a scale of 5), while only 7 respondents gave the highest rating (5). This suggests that while government policies have some influence on solar adoption, they may not be perceived as highly effective by most respondents.

4.31 Major Hurdles To Solar Adoption In Indian Households

Table 4.31

Major Hurdles to Solar Adoption In Indian Households

Options	No. of Respondents
Higher Installation Cost	13
Lack of Awareness	16
Limited Government Support	3
Maintanance Concern	8
Space Constraints	5
Other	8
Total	53

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.31

Interpretation

The table 4.31 and chart 4.31 suggest that lack of awareness (16 respondents) and higher installation costs (13 respondents) are the most significant hurdles to solar adoption in Indian households. Other challenges, such as maintenance concerns (8

respondents) and space constraints (5 respondents), also play a role, but government support appears to be the least cited issue (3 respondents).

4.32 Key Motives for Installing Solar PV

Table 4.32

Key Motives for Installing Solar PV

Options	No. of respondents
Lower Upfront Cost	16
Better Awareness of Benefits	8
Increased Government Subsidies	10
Reduced Electricity Bills	9
Positive Feedback from Others	7
Other	3
Total	53

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.32

Interpretation

The table 4.32 and chart 4.32 highlights that lower upfront cost (16 respondents) and increased government subsidies (10 respondents) are the primary motivators

for installing solar PV systems. Additionally, reduced electricity bills (9 respondents) and better awareness of benefits (8 respondents) also play significant roles, suggesting that financial incentives and awareness campaigns are key drivers for adoption.

4.33 Maintenance & Reliability Concerns

Tables 4.33

Maintenance & Reliability Concerns (1 – 5)

Rating	No. of Respondents
1	5
2	13
3	22
4	9
5	4
Total	53

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.33

Interpretation

The table 4.33 and chart 4.33 clearly indicates that maintenance and reliability concerns are moderately significant, with 41% of respondents (22 people) rating them as 3 on a scale of 5. While only 8% (4 respondents) consider these concerns

very high (rating of 5), a notable portion (25%) rated them as 2, suggesting that while maintenance is a concern, it may not be a major barrier for most respondents.

4.34 Suitability for Household Use

Table 4.34
Suitability for Household Use

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	51	96.22%
No	2	3.78%
Total	53	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Chart 4.34

Interpretation

The table 4.34 and chart 4.34 clearly shows that an overwhelming majority (96.22%) of respondents believe that solar PV systems are suitable for household use, while only a small fraction (3.78%) disagrees. This indicates strong acceptance and perceived feasibility of solar energy for residential applications.

Chapter 5

Findings, Suggestions and Conclusion

5.1 Findings

- Majority of Age (35+) are more likely to adopt solar PV, while younger groups (18-25) show lower participation due to financial constraints.
- Males (64.15%) are the primary decision-makers in solar PV adoption, indicating a gender gap in financial and energy decisions.
- Business owners (33.96%) and salaried employees (24.53%) are the key adopters, while students and retirees have lower involvement.
- Solar PV adoption is higher in rural (54.72%) and semi-urban (37.74%) areas compared to urban regions (7.55%).
- A vast majority (92.45%) of respondents own their homes, making them more likely to invest in solar PV systems.
- Middle-income (39.62%) and upper-income (26.42%) groups dominate solar PV adoption, showing financial capacity as a key factor.
- Most respondents (92.45%) rely on grid electricity, highlighting the challenge of complete solar energy independence.
- Around 71.7% pay over ₹3,000 monthly on electricity, indicating strong cost-saving potential with solar PV.
- A high 88.67% of respondents are aware of solar PV systems, but 11.32% still lack awareness, requiring better outreach.
- Most respondents have only moderate knowledge of solar PV, highlighting the need for technical education on system operations.
- Social media (35.85%) is the top awareness source, while government campaigns (9.43%) have limited impact.

- Over half (52.8%) have partial knowledge of solar PV, while 18.9% lack any understanding of its operation.
- While 74% recognize solar PV's financial benefits, 26% remain unaware, showing the need for better information.
- Most respondents (36 out of 53) view lower electricity bills as the key benefit, while environmental benefits are secondary.
- While 60.37% believe solar PV reduces grid dependence, only 3.77% see it as a full replacement for grid electricity.
- High costs (25 respondents) and maintenance concerns (22 respondents) are the biggest myths, while efficiency doubts are minimal.
- A strong 83.01% of respondents have installed solar PV systems, indicating growing acceptance driven by cost savings and incentives.
- Most users prefer systems between 1KW-6KW, likely balancing affordability and household energy needs.
- The majority (21 out of 44) spent ₹2,00,000-₹3,00,000 on installation, making mid-range investments the most common.
- Lack of awareness (15 respondents) and high upfront costs (12 respondents) are the biggest challenges to adoption.
- Most respondents (23 out of 44) spend ₹5,000-₹10,000 annually on maintenance, indicating moderate upkeep costs.
- The majority (18 out of 44) experienced a 20%-50% reduction in electricity bills after installing solar PV.
- Most respondents (25 out of 44) expect a 3-5 year payback period, showing confidence in solar PV's financial viability.
- While 64% are aware of solar subsidies, 36% remain uninformed, emphasizing the need for better subsidy communication.

- Most respondents (36 out of 44) are ready to invest ₹50,000-₹2,00,000 in solar PV, indicating moderate investment willingness.
- A high 88% of respondents utilize government incentives, showing strong participation in subsidy programs.
- Most respondents (77.27%) found the subsidy process easy, but 22.73% faced difficulties, highlighting areas for improvement.
- While 51% find subsidies effective, 21% disagree, and 28% remain unsure about their impact on adoption.
- Higher subsidies (35.85%) and better awareness campaigns (26.42%) are the most requested additional support measures.
- Most respondents (23 out of 53) rate government policies as moderately effective, suggesting room for improvement.
- Lack of awareness (16 respondents) and high installation costs (13 respondents) are the biggest obstacles to solar PV adoption.
- Lower upfront costs (16 respondents) and increased subsidies (10 respondents) are the key drivers of adoption.
- Most respondents rated maintenance concerns as moderate, meaning they are a factor but not a major deterrent.
- A strong 96.22% of respondents believe solar PV is suitable for residential use, showing high acceptance.

5.2 Suggestions

- Government and private organizations should enhance awareness programs to educate households on solar PV benefits and functionality.
- Streamlining the subsidy application process can encourage more households to adopt solar PV systems with ease.

- Higher subsidies and low-interest financing options can help reduce the burden of high upfront costs.
- Providing better technical knowledge about solar PV system maintenance and operations can boost confidence in adoption.
- Policies should be revised to address adoption barriers and ensure stronger incentives for solar PV users.
- Awareness and adoption efforts should focus more on urban areas where interest is currently low.
- Financial incentives for larger solar PV systems can maximize cost savings and grid independence.
- Public outreach should correct myths about high costs, maintenance, and solar efficiency issues.
- Promoting local manufacturing and service providers can lower costs and make solar PV more accessible.
- Utilizing social media as a key awareness tool can significantly increase outreach and influence adoption decisions.

Conclusion

The study reveals that financial savings, particularly reduced electricity bills, are the primary driver of residential solar PV adoption in India. While awareness levels are relatively high, misconceptions about high costs and maintenance persist, hindering wider adoption. The study highlights the importance of government subsidies, with a majority of respondents utilizing incentives, though some find the application process challenging. Most users expect a payback period of 3-5 years, indicating a favorable return on investment, yet high initial costs remain a barrier.

To enhance adoption, stronger awareness campaigns, simplified subsidy procedures, and increased financial incentives are necessary. Encouraging investment in larger systems, improving technical knowledge, and expanding outreach in urban areas can further drive solar PV growth. Strengthening policy effectiveness will ensure long-term economic and environmental benefits.

Appendix

1. Name –

2. . Age:-

18 - 25

25 - 35

35 – 45

Above 45

3. Gender: -

-Male

-Female

4. Occupation:-

-Student

- Salaried Employee

- Business Owner

-Retired

-Other

5. 5. Where do you reside ?

- Urban

-Semi-Urban

- Rural

6. Do you own or rent your residence?

-Own

-Rent

7. What is your Average monthly household income?

- Below ₹25,000

- ₹25,000 - ₹50,000

-₹50,000 - ₹1,00,000

-Above ₹1,00,000

8. How do you currently manage your electricity consumption?

-Only grid electricity

- Grid electricity with backup (generator/inverter)

-Grid electricity with solar PV system

- Fully dependent on solar PV system
- Battery storage system
- No storage system, relying only on solar during daylight hours.

9. What is your average monthly electricity bill?

- Less than ₹1,000
- ₹1,000 - ₹3,000
- ₹3,000-₹5,000
- Above ₹5,000

10. Are you aware of residential Solar PV systems?

- Yes
- No

11. On a scale of 1 to 5, how familiar are you with how Solar PV systems work? (1 = Not familiar at all 5 = Very familiar)

12. How did you first learn about Solar PV systems?

- Social media
- News/articles
- Friends/family
- Government campaigns
- Solar companies

- Other

13. Do you know how a solar PV system works?

-Yes

- No

-Somewhat

14. Are you aware of the long-term cost savings associated with Solar PV systems?

-Yes

- No

15. What do you think are the primary benefits of Solar PV systems?

- Reduced electricity bills

- Environmental benefits

-Energy independence

-Government incentives and subsidies

16. Do you think solar PV systems can completely replace traditional electricity sources?

-Yes, fully replace grid electricity

-No, but can significantly reduce dependence

-No, solar PV alone is not sufficient

17. What do you think is the biggest misconception about solar PV systems?

- Too expensive
- High maintenance required
- Doesn't work on cloudy days
- Not enough government support

18. Do you currently have a solar PV system installed at your residence?

- Yes
- No

19. If yes, what was the total upfront cost of installation?

- Less than ₹1,00,000
- ₹1,00,000 - ₹2,00,000
- ₹2,00,000 - ₹3,00,000
- Above ₹3,00,000

20. If no, what is the primary reason for not installing one?

- High initial cost
- Lack of awareness
- Uncertainty about savings/benefits
- Maintenance concern
- Space constraints

21. What are your average annual maintenance expenses for the Solar PV system?

- Less than ₹5,000
- ₹5,000 - ₹10,000
- ₹10,000 - ₹20,000
- Above ₹20,000

22. How has your electricity bill changed after installing a solar PV system?

- Decreased significantly (More than 50%)
- Decreased moderately (20%-50%)
- Slight decrease (Less than 20%)
- No noticeable change

23. What is your expected payback period for a Solar PV system investment?

- Less than 3 years
- 3-5 years
- 5-7 years
- More than 7 years

24. If you haven't installed a Solar PV system, what is the maximum upfront cost you are willing to pay?

- Less than ₹50,000
- ₹50,000 - ₹1,00,000

-₹1,00,000 - ₹2,00,000

-Above ₹2,00,000

25. Are you aware of the government policies and subsidies available for Solar PV systems?

-Yes

- No

26. Have you availed of any government subsidies or incentives for installing a Solar PV system?

-Yes

- No

27. If yes, how easy was the process of applying for subsidies?

- Very easy

-Somewhat easy

- Difficult

- Very difficult

28. Do you think government subsidies are sufficient to encourage more people to install solar PV systems?

-Yes

- No

- Not sure

29. What additional support do you expect from the government to encourage Solar PV adoption?

- Higher subsidies
- Better awareness campaigns
- Simplified application process
- Tax benefits
- Other

30. how effective do you think government policies are in promoting Solar PV adoption?

- rating from (1-5)

31. What do you think is the biggest barrier to solar PV adoption in India?

- High installation costs
- Lack of awareness
- Limited government support
- Maintenance concerns
- Space constraints

32. What would motivate you to install a Solar PV system? (Select all that apply)

- Lower upfront costs
- Better awareness of benefits
- Increased government subsidies

-Positive feedback from others

-Reduced electricity bills

-Other

33. how concerned are you about the maintenance of Solar PV systems? (1 = Not concerned at all, 5 = Very concerned)

34. Do you think Solar PV systems are suitable for your household's energy needs?

-Yes

-No

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